

PRE-SERVICE TEACHER'S CONTENT AND PEDAGOGICAL
KNOWLEDGE IN ALVAN IKOKU FEDERAL COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, OWERRI
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Abstract

The study investigated pre-service teacher's content and pedagogical knowledge in Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri. The study adopted the survey research design. Simple random sampling technique was used to select three schools (Languages, Science and Education) from schools in Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri. From each school, 110 pre-service teachers in 300 level were randomly selected, making a total of 330 pre-service teachers. Two research instruments were used for data collection: Pre-service teachers' Content Knowledge Questionnaire ($r=0.84$) and Preservice teachers' Pedagogical Content Knowledge Questionnaire ($r=0.78$). Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of frequency count, percentage, mean and standard deviation. Findings of the study revealed that the majority of the pre-service teachers (78.0%) had a high content knowledge and 68.1 % had a high pedagogical content knowledge. It could be concluded from the study that pre-service teacher's content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge were high. Based on the findings, it was recommended that lecturers should adopt methods of teaching that will enhance pre-service teachers' content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge. Pre-

service teachers should not only have content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge of the courses they study but allow them to reflect on their teaching when they are fully employed to teach.

Keywords: Pre-service teachers, Content knowledge, Pedagogical content knowledge

Introduction

Pre-service teachers must go through the right training to qualify them for the post of teacher. The education acquired by pre-service teachers with the desire to become professionals in the field of teaching is called teacher education (Oyebanji, 2010). Teachers of high quality in skills and knowledge promote high quality in teaching. It is essential for teachers to be knowledgeable in their subject areas (Olatunji, Bateye & Fakeye, 2021). It is therefore necessary for pre-service teachers to build and develop their teaching expertise. This involves, knowing what to teach and how to teach it and methods to be adopted to teach a particular topic.

Pre-service teachers that are adequately prepared will impact positively on students and the educational sector. On the contrary, the negative impact would be their low quality and ineffectiveness. Therefore, it is impossible to think of a school without a well-defined teacher training programme because, teachers who are well prepared; produce quality students (Anangisye, 2010). Therefore, adequate preparation of teachers in colleges of education is imperative. Some of the benefits of teacher preparation programmes are reduction in teachers' attrition rate and high student achievement.

Despite the importance attached to adequate preparation of pre-service teachers, it was reported that the preparation of pre-service teachers at some colleges of education is below expectation. Efforts to address this problem have made scholars and researchers to carry out numerous studies on lecturers, students and the curriculum. All these studies contributed immensely to teacher preparation programmes in colleges of education but with less research focus on the impact of pre-service teachers' content and pedagogical knowledge. Content Knowledge provides an overview of how lecturers conceptualise the content of a particular subject matter or topic. It is developed by asking lecturers to think about what they consider to be the "big ideas" associated with teaching a given topic for a particular level(s) based on their experience of teaching that topic. Lecturers must be knowledgeable in their area because if they are not enlightened in the courses they teach, then the hope of effectiveness is not ascertained.

Teachers must possess the knowledge and skills needed to attain the goal and must be able to use that knowledge and skills if the goals are to be achieved. It has been established that there is a high correlation between what teachers know and what they teach. Thus, the ability to teach effectively depends on the teachers' knowledge of the subject matter (Adigun, 2019). Teachers are handicapped if they are unfamiliar with the body of knowledge taught and teachers' characteristics is subject specific. Adigun (2019) stated in their study that nobody could teach what he

does not understand. Teachers must thoroughly understand the content of what they teach. Shulman (1987) views pedagogical content knowledge as teachers' interpretations and transformations of subject-matter knowledge in the context of facilitating student learning. Shulman further proposed several key elements of pedagogical content knowledge: (1) knowledge of representations of subject matter (content knowledge); (2) understanding of students' conceptions of the subject and the learning and teaching implications that were associated with the specific subject matter; and (3) general pedagogical knowledge (or teaching strategies). To complete what he called the knowledge base for teaching, he included other elements: (4) curriculum knowledge; (5) knowledge of educational contexts; and (6) knowledge of the purposes of education.

Pedagogical Content Knowledge Model was introduced by Shulman in 1986. This model has influenced many studies. Pedagogical Content Knowledge was not initially considered as a separate knowledge category but as part of content knowledge that helped teachers to achieve better results in their teaching. Later in 1987, Shulman presented Pedagogical Content Knowledge as a separate knowledge category that is dependent on teachers' knowledge of the subject matter and their ability to transform content knowledge for students to be able to understand the subject matter irrespective of their background for their learning difficulties.

Although, Shulman (1986) was the one who introduced the idea of Pedagogical Content Knowledge, it was Grossman (1990) who later systematised and created a comprehensive model of all components of teacher's knowledge base (Fernandez, 2014). According to the model, four components are intertwined and resulted into teachers' knowledge base. These are General Pedagogical Knowledge, Content knowledge, Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Knowledge of Context. Pedagogical Content Knowledge is central in this model and it is considered as the force that can transform pedagogical knowledge with the contribution of content and context.

Pedagogical Content Knowledge Model is relevant to this study because pre-service teachers' content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge and learning environment are essential to good teaching. Integration of teachers' pedagogical knowledge (what pre-service teachers know about teaching) and content knowledge (what they know about what they teach) is referred to as pedagogical content knowledge. For teachers to exhibit their pedagogical content knowledge or content knowledge very well, a good learning environment is essential.

Teachers' pedagogical content Knowledge is one of the most influential factors contributing to students' learning and achievement. It takes up a prominent role in that it connects subject matter knowledge and teachers' understanding of how to teach content to students. Thereby, pedagogical content knowledge is the knowledge to make the subject matter accessible to students (Kleickmann, Richer, Bunter, Elsner, Besser, Krauss & Baumert, 2013). This is understood as the combination of content and pedagogy that is uniquely the province of teachers, their special form of professional understanding (Shulman, 1987).

Grossman, Wilson and Shulman (1989) describe pedagogical content knowledge as the knowledge of the subject and its organising structures. Similarly, Ball, Thames and Phelps (2008) argue that pedagogical content knowledge goes beyond the teachers' subject mastery. Teachers' pedagogical content knowledge is usually considered as necessary prerequisite for cognitive activation (Baumert, Kunter, Blum, Brunner, Voss, Jordan & Tsai 2010). It can be assumed that high level of pedagogical content knowledge allows teachers to devise learning environments that challenge and support students' learning processes, with highly knowledgeable teachers being able to anticipate students' difficulties and adaptively respond when students encounter problems. Cognitive as the facets of instructional quality which captures highly structured, cognitively challenging instructional processes and pedagogical content knowledge were found to be highly correlated (Baumert, Kunter, Blum, Brunner, Voss, Jordan & Tsai, 2010).

Adigun (2019) asserts that one of the unique features of pedagogical content knowledge is that it bridges the gap between the teachers' content knowledge and the practice of education. This is because pedagogical content knowledge ensures the discussions of content(subjects) are relevant to teaching and that discussions of teaching retain attention to the content (subject). Teachers who possess pedagogical content knowledge can effectively create representations for concepts, recognise students' preconceptions, misconceptions of content and sequence curriculum to enhance students' learning" (Shulman, 1986). It is the knowledge of, rationale behind, planning for, and act of teaching a specific piece of subject matter, in a specific context, to support students' learning of the material Teacher and teaching quality, including teacher knowledge about content and pedagogy, can greatly impact students' achievement (Gess-Newsome, 2015). However, content knowledge alone, while recognised as an imperative knowledge base by researchers, is not the only type of knowledge teachers need to be effective (Baumert, Kunter, Blum, Brunner, Voss, Jordan & Tsai, 2010).

Many studies such as Kleickmann, Richer, Bunter, Elsner, Besser, Krauss & Baumert (2013), Olatunji, S.O, Bateye, O.R & Fakeye, D.O. (2021) and Robinson (2017) have shown that teacher's content and pedagogical knowledge are strong determinants of students' learning outcomes but to the best knowledge of the researcher, these factors have not been investigated, especially in Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri. Therefore, this study investigated the pre-service teachers' content and pedagogical knowledge in Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri.

Statement of the Problem

For anyone to be qualified to be a teacher, he or she must undergo the right training to promote high quality in teaching and education. Pre-service teachers that are adequately prepared will impact the lives of students positively. In spite of the importance attached to adequate preparation of pre-service teachers especially at the colleges of education, the preparation of pre-service teachers at this level of

education is still below standard. As a way of addressing this problem, scholars and researchers have carried out numerous studies on lecturers, students and the curriculum. All these studies came up with good insights into teacher preparation programmes in colleges of education, but with less research attention paid to pre-service teacher's content and pedagogical knowledge especially in Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri. Therefore, this study investigated pre-service teacher's content and pedagogical knowledge in Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri.

Objectives of the Study

The study determined the following:

- i. the level of pre-service teachers' content knowledge
- ii. the level of preservice teachers' pedagogical content knowledge

Research Questions

Two research questions were raised to guide the study. These are:

- i. What is the level of pre-service teachers' content knowledge?
- ii. What is the level of preservice teachers' pedagogical content knowledge?

Methodology

The study adopted the survey research design. Simple random sampling technique was used to select three schools (Languages, Science and Education) from schools in Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri. From each school, 110 pre-service teachers in 300 level were randomly selected, making a total of 330 pre-service teachers. Two research instruments were used for data collection: Pre-service teachers' Content Knowledge Questionnaire ($r=0.84$) and Preservice teachers' Pedagogical Content Knowledge Questionnaire ($r=0.78$). Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of frequency count and percentage.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of pre-service teachers' content knowledge?

Table 1: Level of pre-service teachers' content knowledge

Score Interval	Frequency	Percent
0 - 9 (Low)	30	9.5
10 - 19 (Average)	40	12.5
20 and above (High)	260	78.0
Total	330	100.0

Table 1 shows the level of pre-service teachers' content knowledge. The result indicates that majority (260; 78.0%) of the pre-service teachers has high score (20 and above) in content knowledge test, 40 (12.5%) has average score (10-19) while

the remaining 30 (9.5%) has low score (0 – 9). The table also shows that the level of pre-service teachers' content knowledge is high. The result implies that the level of pre-service teachers' content knowledge is high.

Research Question 2: What is the level of pre-service teachers' pedagogical content knowledge?

Table: Level of pre-service teachers' pedagogical content knowledge

Score Interval	Frequency	Percent
0 - 9 (Low)	42	13.1
10 - 19 (Average)	60	18.8
20 and above (High)	228	68.1
Total	330	100.0

Table 2 shows the level of pre-service teachers' pedagogical content knowledge. The result indicates that majority (228; 68.1%) of the pre-service teachers has high score (20 and above) in pedagogical content knowledge test, 60 (18.8%) has average score (10-19) while the remaining 42 (13.1%) has low score (0 – 9). The table also shows that the level of pre-service teachers' pedagogical content knowledge is high. The result implies that the level of pre-service teachers' pedagogical content knowledge is high.

Discussion of Findings

Findings revealed that the level of pre-service teachers' content knowledge was high. This study has provided empirical evidence on pre-service teachers' content knowledge. This would in turn, lead to providing improvement guide for teaching and learning in colleges of education. This finding is similar to the study of Robinson (2017) who reported that science teachers have the content knowledge of the subjects they teach. He reported that lack of science content knowledge could limit teacher's ability to plan effectively and deliver science lessons. Also, Adediwura & Bada (2007) reported that nobody could teach what he does not understand. Teachers must thoroughly understand the content of what they teach. In contrary to this finding, Solis (2009) who found out that teachers' content knowledge had nothing to do with students' performance.

Results revealed that the level of pre-service teachers' pedagogical content knowledge was high. This study has provided empirical evidence on pre-service teachers' pedagogical content knowledge. This would add to the existing body of research on colleges of education pre-service teachers. This is in line with the study of Kleickmann, Richer, Bunter, Elsner, Besser, Krauss & Baumert (2013) who reported in their separate studies that pedagogical content knowledge takes up a prominent role in that it connects subject matter knowledge and teachers' understanding of how to teach contents to students. Also, Ghanney and Agyei (2021) revealed that junior high school social studies teachers possessed some levels of

pedagogical content knowledge. Pedagogical content knowledge influence teacher's assessment practice. Olatunji, Bateye & Fakeye (2021) revealed that English language teachers possessed high level of pedagogical content knowledge. This finding is against the study of Solis (2009) that pedagogical content knowledge had nothing to do with students' performance.

Conclusion

The study has shown that pre-service teacher's content and pedagogical knowledge were high. Based on the findings, this study has provided a better understanding that pre-service teachers content and pedagogical knowledge have impact on pre-service teachers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, it was recommended that lecturers should adopt methods of teaching that will enhance pre-service teachers' content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge. Pre-service teachers should not only have content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge of the courses they study but allow them to reflect on their teaching when they are fully employed to teach.

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